
ENHANCING TRANSLATION SKILLS WITH GAME TECHNOLOGIES

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Abstract: This article explores the use of game technologies in foreign language education at the university level. It analyzes game technologies from the perspective of their use in developing translation competence among university students.

Keywords: game technologies, translation, translation competence, university students, higher education.

It is well known that gaming activities are one of the primary types of activities for students, as games represent a form of activity aimed at developing social skills and competencies needed in the future. Performing various functions—entertainment, communicative, game therapy, diagnostic, corrective, intercultural communication, as well as socialization and self-realization functions—gaming activities become an indispensable element of the educational process at all stages [2].

The use of game technologies in foreign language lessons is a necessity, as only in game situations do students and educators have the opportunity to recreate communicative situations close to real-life communication scenarios. By game technology, we understand a given situation based on social experience [3].

In pedagogy and foreign language teaching methodology at the university level, game technologies imply a complex of interconnected actions aimed at achieving specific results. Any game technology includes several stages—from goal setting to self-analysis. At each stage of academic life, game technologies have their characteristics. For example, in the university setting, where students are already mature and seeking professional identity, game technologies should be used in a way that aligns with their aspirations for professional self-realization and community engagement. Unlike in secondary education, game technologies in universities should be oriented towards complex speech activities and sophisticated scenarios that simulate professional environments and real-world challenges. As university students navigate the transition from academic environments to professional spheres, they particularly benefit from game technologies that foster critical thinking, problem-solving, and professional skills essential for their future careers. Thus, the orientation of game technologies at this level is towards developing a high degree of language and professional competencies. University students are often driven by the need for professional self-definition, and they seek to showcase their intellectual and

professional abilities, as "learning is complemented by self-education, acquiring a deeper personal meaning" [4].

The application of game technologies in university foreign language education is crucial because the preparation and implementation of the technology involve a broad spectrum of pedagogical and methodological tasks—from forming certain specialized academic and professional skills and abilities (didactic tasks) to fostering communicativeness, critical thinking, and professional demeanor (educational tasks). Universities provide an advanced platform for further developing a significant number of professional competencies at a higher level than in secondary education. One such competence is translation competence or the ability to translate professionally. Developing translation competence is an intricate process that begins early in educational journeys but reaches advanced levels in university settings where students engage deeply with complex texts and professional translation scenarios. From the onset of their university education, students encounter increasingly challenging translation tasks that necessitate a sophisticated understanding of both source and target languages. Translation skills are honed through intensive practice in reading, writing, listening, and speaking exercises that are embedded within the curriculum and further explored through game-based learning scenarios that mimic real translation tasks in various professional contexts [5].

The process of refining translation skills involves meticulous work on linguistic nuances, idiomatic expressions, and culturally laden texts, where both active and passive memory play significant roles. This is because the processed linguistic and extralinguistic material is often retained deeply but can be readily activated in professional translation settings.

Translation activity at the university level is a sophisticated type of speech activity, based on proficient command over comprehensive linguistic skills. Thus, the effective development and refinement of translation competence can only occur if the enhancement of linguistic competence, encompassing advanced lexical-grammatical and phonetic components, is continuously pursued.

Translation competence at the university level involves a complex array of competencies. Linguistic competence enables students to analyze complex linguistic materials and select appropriate lexical-grammatical structures and phrases in both the target and source languages. Developed text-forming competence allows students to construct and interpret texts of various types and complexities to meet specific professional translation needs.

Through this competence, students learn to perceive and produce texts as coherent wholes. The communicative component of translation competence cultivates the ability to utilize background knowledge effectively to navigate and resolve complex professional communication scenarios.

Additionally, technical competence is critical at the university level, as it involves the ability to research, analyze, and apply information using advanced digital technologies [5]. As V.N. Komissarov noted, "the process of developing professional translation competence leads to the formation of a unique linguistic personality, distinguished from a 'normal', non-translational personality. These distinctions manifest across all key aspects of communication: linguistic, text-forming, communicative, personal, and technical-professional" [cited from: 5].

The effective incorporation of game technologies into university curricula for foreign languages necessitates creating conditions that motivate students to pursue continual professional growth and self-improvement. Here, game technologies are invaluable as they provide dynamic, engaging platforms for simulating real-world translation scenarios that resonate with students' professional aspirations. Often, translation activities at the university level include advanced forms of translation such as conference interpreting, literary translation, and technical translation. These forms of professional translation activity should be integral to the game technologies deployed in teaching foreign languages at universities. Considering the potential of game technologies to foster translation competence among university students involves an initial phase of planning and scenario development. The most effective game technology for developing translation competence in university foreign language education appears to be the business game. According to G.P. Shchedrovitsky, a business game is "a pedagogical method for modeling various management and production situations, the goal of which is to train individuals and groups in decision-making [cited from: 1]. Serving as a form of social-pedagogical organization of life, business games can address numerous educational and extracurricular challenges at the university level. A business game, like any game technology, necessarily includes motivational, orientational, content-operational, value-volitional, and evaluative components, each demanding active participation from students and interactive engagement with educators. The preparatory stage of a business game at the university level involves creating a detailed action plan and developing scenarios that reflect real professional challenges and contexts. For instance, conducting a role-playing game titled "The Profession of a Conference Interpreter" requires familiarizing students with the intricacies of this specific type of translation activity, highlighting the necessity for high-level language preparation and extensive background knowledge relevant to the translation tasks at hand. By proposing this type of role-playing game, educators can revisit and reinforce grammatical structures and vocabulary, thereby motivating students by emphasizing that a professional translator must consistently maintain peak linguistic proficiency. In the subsequent phase of the business game, students are introduced to the theme of the event and assume roles according to the scenario crafted for the simulation. Here,

educators might employ several strategies. One approach involves presenting students with a predefined scenario, meticulously prepared by the educator with aligned educational materials—lexical glossaries, grammatical exercises tailored to the curriculum, and authentic texts that serve as the foundation for foreign language discourse. In this scenario, the student's role is relatively passive, with their primary task being to learn and apply the material according to the educator's structured plan. Alternatively, a more interactive strategy requires students to engage actively under direct educator supervision. In this dynamic setting, the educator's role is to propose a theme for the translation-related business game and maintain subtle oversight over the student organizers. This approach grants students substantial autonomy and significant responsibility, as all decision-making responsibilities rest with them. Typically, this type of business game enhances group cohesion among students and helps identify both overt and potential leaders. Regarding the development of translation competence, improvement occurs throughout all phases of the business game. At the preparatory stage, students may either tackle additional tasks on specific grammatical and lexical rules set by the educator (first strategy) or undertake research to locate authentic materials on a designated translation topic, which must include the necessary grammatical constructions and lexical-phraseological units (second strategy). This research-oriented approach at the preparatory stage compels students to engage with a considerably larger volume of linguistic material, undoubtedly aiding the enhancement of their language competence. During the role distribution and functional assignment phase, students can also practice translating from the foreign language to their native language and vice versa, both orally and in written form. This practice can be seamlessly integrated into both academic and informal settings, further enriching the learning experience. In the final phase of the business game, students actively participate in the role-playing exercise, where they alternately assume the roles of a 'foreign guest' who does not speak the local language on any given topic, or a translator, performing consecutive interpretation tasks. If the language proficiency of the students is particularly high, they may also be challenged to engage in literary translation, perhaps through a "literary-translation" competition designed to simulate real-world literary interpretation scenarios. The concluding stage of the business game involves a comprehensive debriefing session where the execution of the role-play is critically assessed to identify both its strengths and areas for improvement. This review session also provides an opportunity to address any linguistic or interpretative challenges encountered during the game, thereby facilitating further development of translation competence. Ultimately, performing lexical exercises that focus on practicing and activating vocabulary, including stable expressions, idioms, phrasal verbs, and lexical compatibility; engaging with a broad spectrum of reading texts from contemporary authentic sources, supplemented by

exercises that enhance students' reading interest; fostering active participation in spoken language practice; cultivating critical thinking through evidence-based discussions; and conducting practical assessments—all contribute to the development of translation competence through the use of game technologies, specifically role-playing games, because these activities elevate students' language preparedness for professional translation tasks and support the growth of their translation competencies at the university level.

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